

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF COPPER, NICKEL AND COBALT^{II} WITH BENZIMIDAZOLE AND THEIR MAGNETIC PROPERTIES

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Benzimidazole forms stable inner-metallic complexes with copper, nickel and cobalt^{II} of the general formula $M(C_7H_5N_2)_2$, where M represents an atom of Cu, Ni or Co^{II}. Magnetic properties of these complexes have been studied and their structures discussed.

Benzimidazole, $C_7H_5N_2$ (I), which may serve as a bidentate group, forms quite stable four-fold inner-metallic complexes with bivalent copper, nickel and cobalt. With copper, in addition, it gives rise to an unstable associated or additive complex of the cuprammine type. These two copper complexes can be represented by formulae II and III.

The compound (II) is red and very stable, while (III) is blue and unstable, readily changing into the red form with the separation of benzimidazole.

The red compound gives a magnetic moment of 1.81 Bohr magneton and the blue, 1.95. The magnetic moment of the blue compound agrees with the value for Cu^{++} in simple cupric salts, viz. 1.90 to 2.20.

Rây and Sen (this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 473) have demonstrated that penetration complexes of copper with planar dsp^2 bonds show a comparatively low magnetic moment lying between 1.72 and 1.82 Bohrs than its ionic or tetrahedral complexes or even planar complexes of sp^2d type for which the moment value agrees with that of Cu^{++} in simple cupric salts, viz. 1.90 to 2.20. The authors attributed this change to the greater quenching effect of the orbital moment of the single unpaired electron in the penetration complexes of copper with planar dsp^2 bonds than in its associated complexes with ionic tetrahedral or planar sp^2d bonds. For, in the former, the electron is promoted to a higher level where it is more effectively exposed to the fields of neighbouring atoms and ions. Hence, in the penetration complexes of copper the magnetic moment approaches that value, theoretically expected on the Bose-Stoner formula, viz. 1.73 Bohr. It may therefore be concluded on the above reasoning that the red, stable benzimidazole complex of copper is of the penetration type with planar dsp^2 bonds. The blue unstable sulphate is an associated complex of the ionic tetrahedral or planar sp^2d type.

The magnetic moment of the nickel complex is 3.09 Bohrs. According to Bose-Stoner formula the moment for simple Ni^{++} ion is 2.83 Bohrs. The observed magnetic moments for simple Ni^{++} ion, however, varies from 3.20 to 3.44. Thus, the observed value for the benzimidazole complex of nickel agrees more or less with that of simple

Ni^{++} ion in spite of its being a fairly stable inner-metallic complex. Magnetochemically it really belongs to the associated type.

The cobaltous bisbenzimidazole, an unusually stable complex of the inner-metallic type, presents an interesting example from the magnetochemical point of view. Its moment of 3.85 Bohrs is lower than that for simple Co^{++} ion in simple cobaltous salts, which lies between 4.5 and 5.0. The value is, however, higher than that for cobaltous complexes of penetration type, viz. 2.66 Bohrs, as has been reported by Rây and Ghosh (this *Journal*, 1943, 20, 323). The value agrees with that of some of the cobaltous complexes of the associated type studied (cf. Mellor and Goldacre, *Proc. Roy. Soc. N. S. Wales*, 1940, 73, 233).

EXPERIMENTAL

Benzimidazole was prepared according to the method described by Wundt (*Ber.*, 1878, 11, 826). *o*-Phenylethylenediamine (54 g.) was heated with 90% formic acid (32 c.c.) on the water-bath for 2 hours. The mixture was then treated with 10% caustic soda till alkaline. The liberated benzimidazole was filtered and purified by recrystallisation from hot water, m.p. 171-72°.

Copper bisbenzimidazole was obtained as a bright red precipitate by adding ammonia to a mixture of copper sulphate and benzimidazole in aqueous solution. The precipitate was filtered and washed thoroughly with hot water and alcohol and dried in air. Dilute acids decomposed the complex with the formation of simple copper salts. [Found: Cu, 21.41; N, 18.86. $Cu(C_7H_5N_2)_2$ requires Cu, 21.36; N, 18.32 per cent].

Copper tetrakisBenzimidazole Sulphate.—When a concentrated solution of copper sulphate was treated with an alcoholic solution of benzimidazole a blue precipitate was formed at once. This was filtered and washed first with cold water and then with alcohol and dried in air. The substance is unstable and readily changes to the red compound described above. The dry substance is, however, fairly stable. {Found: Cu, 9.36; N, 16.73; SO_4 , 14.20. $[Cu(C_7H_5N_2)]SO_4 \cdot 2.5 H_2O$ requires Cu, 9.39; N, 16.55; SO_4 , 14.18 per cent}.

Nickel bisbenzimidazole was obtained as a dirty violet precipitate by adding ammoniacal nickel sulphate (cobalt free) solution to that of benzimidazole in hot water. The substance was washed and dried as in the previous case. [Found: Ni, 18.81; N, 18.20. $Ni(C_7H_5N_2)_2$ requires Ni, 18.88; N, 18.04 per cent].

Cobalt bisbenzimidazole separated as a brilliant violet crystalline precipitate when very dilute ammonia was added dropwise to a mixture of cobalt sulphate (nickel free) and benzimidazole in warm water. The precipitate was washed with cold water and alcohol and dried in air. It resembles the corresponding copper and nickel compounds in properties. [Found: Co, 20.12; N, 19.15. $Co(C_7H_5N_2)_2$ requires Co, 19.90; N, 19.29 per cent].

Measurement of Magnetic Susceptibility.—The susceptibility of these compounds was measured according to Gouy's method as described by Rây and Ghosh (*loc. cit.*). The molecular susceptibility has been corrected for atomic and ionic diamagnetism.

From the corrected atomic susceptibility for the central metal ion, the value of its magnetic moment in terms of Bohr magnetons was calculated from the relation

$$\mu_B = 2.84 \sqrt{\chi_A \times T}$$

Results of magnetic measurement are given below.

TABLE I

Substance.	Temp.	$\chi_g \times 10^6$.	$\chi_M \times 10^6$.	$\chi_A \times 10^6$.	μ_B .
$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{N}_2)_2$	32°	4.20	1249.5	1379.8	1.81
$[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{N}_2)_4]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	"	1.88	1264.3	1584.6	1.96
$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{N}_2)_2$	"	13.10	3834.4	3964.7	3.04
$\text{Co}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{N}_2)_2$	"	20.73	5955.4	6086.1	3.85

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